

**ASSESSING THE INFLUENCE OF METHODOLOGICAL CHOICES ON
OUTCOMES IN EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH****Jomailah J. Hadjiansary**

Teacher I, Lumbocan Elementary School, Philippines

Charrie Fe C. Concepcion

Teacher III, Ozamis City School of Arts and Trades, Philippines

Geo P. Alega

Teacher I, Marciano Amancio Integrated School, Philippines

Liberty C. Jonem

Teacher III, Clarin National High School, Philippines

ABSTRACT

A research paper's methodology shed light on how a researcher would collect or generate the data and demonstrate how these data would be treated. This study assessed the influence of methodological choices on outcome in educational research as perceived by teachers. It employed a descriptive correlational research design. It was participated by 200 randomly selected public school teachers in the Philippines. The study used a developed survey-questionnaire. The study found out that teachers highly perceived methodological choices as significant but critical aspect to consider in conducting a research study in terms of research design to use, sampling techniques and data analysis techniques. The study also concluded that teachers highly perceived methodological choices as highly technical because it laid the foundation of a well-established scholarly work emphasizing applicability of practice, reliability of results and validity of findings. On the other hand, there was a moderate positive correlation between the perceived significance of methodological choices in terms of research design and the perceived influence of methodological choices in developing educational researches in terms of applicability of practice, which indicated that as teachers perceived the significance of methodological choices in research design to be higher, they also tend to perceive a greater influence of these choices on the applicability of research findings in educational practice.

Keywords:*Methodological choices, influence, assessment, critical, research design, applicability of practice*

INTRODUCTION

Writing a research paper is one of the most critical aspects in the pursuit of excellence in various fields. In this line, the development and formulation of education-related researches is also seen as one of the crucial forms in research writing. Teachers as researchers and writers of their research work are often confronted with the difficulty of writing their research papers from selecting the topics to finalizing the research work. Research writing as scientific endeavor required tedious processes which teachers as researchers are obligated to observe and follow highly complex scientific process. From the determination on the current conditions, problems, issues or challenges they observed in their respective field, formulation of research questions, selection of appropriate research methodology, interpretation and discussion of findings to comprehensive narration of research work's impact in education as their field of interests. Further, writing an education-related research requires more rigorous process because of the certain factors which teachers consider such as their time to be allocated in doing such research work, their means in accessing their respondents and their style of presenting the results and findings of their work arising from relevant data analysis method they used. It is within this line, writing education-related research also institutes a higher level of thinking where teachers as researchers are expected to lay empirical evidences that would support their assertions in the study they have conducted. Thus, writing education-related research put greater emphasis on the comprehensive identification of the problems,

gaps and conditions surrounding the educational system. In the Philippine educational context, writing educational researches provides significant scientific opportunities for teachers to fundamentally understand the pressing situations of education as contextualized based on their exposure, experiences and perceptions. In developing educational researches, teachers acted as the primary orchestrator of such scholarly work because they were the ones who have direct exposure and experiences in the educational settings specifically in the teaching and learning process. Usual forms of educational researches which were administered by teachers specially among public basic education institutions were classroom-based action research, applied research and quantitative researches. These were the common types of educational researches they have employed in order to scientifically examine the prevailing conditions they encountered as teachers.

The development and construction of educational researches are not bounded nor limited on pedagogy but as school was a formalized social institutions, all conditions which teachers observed relating to school operations, instructions, achievement of quality education, participation and academic success of the learners were some parts of the whole which circulate in public educational system. Teachers are expected to conduct comprehensive educational researches as they deliver instruction across the subjects they handle among basic education system in the country. A research paper typically embodied the scientific assertions by which teachers claim based on the evidences they have gathered, organized and interpreted. However, teachers found it challenging to select appropriate research methods and present logical and comprehensive research methodology when developing an educational research. The choice and proper selection on research methods and logical presentation of research methodology in educational researches are critical section of a research paper as these section under specific chapter, present the technicalities and scientific substance of the paper. It is where the actual methods to be used and scientific process including selection of the respondents, formulation of research instruments, data collection procedure, data analysis employed and data analysis utilized are to be presented clearly and precisely. The technical aspect of a research paper could be found on the research methodology chapter which are also dissected into several sections based on the standard format of the institutions.

In this line, the researchers observed that most of teachers including their colleagues found it challenging to select or choose appropriate research method to be used when developing educational researches. In addition, the researchers observed that most teachers fail to select appropriate research method and fail to logically present the methodology section because of non-coherence of narration and irrelevance of the study's context to the chosen research methodology. Apparent failure of teachers as observed by the researchers is the inappropriateness of research method or design, non-consistent sampling techniques and erroneous data analysis techniques. Gathering evidence on research impact of methodological research from variety of sources has enabled the researchers to obtain multiple indicators and thus, demonstrate broad impact of methodological research (Bructon et al., 2014). Model evaluation in research were caused by many methodological decisions, the choice of data filtering and cross validation setting (Effenberger & Pelanek, 2020). Conducting empirical research on an emerging phenomenon that cannot be analyzed with existing conceptual tools was a challenges. The considerations have led to the idea of high mobility of methodological choices in conducting researches (Ravalet et al., 2019). While research offered considerable potential for generation of insights, the challenge of developing and applying research methodology raised complex issues (Coulter et al., 2014). The synergistic used proper research design and methodology allowed the researchers to comprehensively examine the context and nature of the study by means of creating proper steps, processes and procedures (Bell et al., 2022). This study filled a knowledge gap since most of the researchers only focused on the implications of selecting proper research methodology in conducting research. Hence, they failed to assess the influence of methodological choices on outcomes in education research. Thus, this gap was filled by this study. Apparently, the study was significant as it may provide data as basis for the development of intervention plan which could help teacher-researchers in considering their methodological choices in formulating highly credible educational researches. Also, results of the study may provide evidences in the formulation of localized or school-based research policy emphasizing the right procedures and processes in selecting proper research methodology. By comprehensively educating teacher-researchers on the proper processes in selecting proper research methodology, they may be able to formulate highly impactful educational researches.

OBJECTIVES

This study assessed teachers' perceptions on the influence of methodological choices on outcomes of educational researches as perceived by teachers. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

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1. How teachers' perceived the significance of methodological choices in conducting educational researches in terms of research design to use, sampling techniques and data analysis techniques?
2. How teachers' perceived the influence of methodological choices in developing educational researches in terms of validity of findings, reliability of results and applicability of practice?
3. Is there a significant relationship between teachers' perceptions on the significance of methodological choices and the perceived influence of methodological choices in developing educational researches?

METHODOLOGY

The study used descriptive correlational research in order to assess teachers' perceptions on the influence of methodological choices on outcomes of educational researches. Descriptive aspect of the study fell on the determination of teachers' perception on the significance of methodological choices in conducting educational researches and their perceived influence of methodological choices in developing educational researches. On one hand, correlational aspect of the study fell in the examination of teachers' perceptions on the significance of methodological choices and the perceived influenced of methodological choices in developing educational researches. The study used a researcher made survey-questionnaire which was subjected to validation and reliability testing. It contained two (2) parts, for part 1, it contained items about the perceptions of teachers on the significance of methodological choices in conducting educational researches and part 2, contained items about the perceptions of teachers on the influence of methodological choices in developing educational researches. Under the validation process, the developed survey-questionnaire was rated as "Outstanding" whereas it signified that all items were congruent to the research objectives. Meanwhile, items under part 1 obtained a Cronbach Alpha result of ($\alpha=.912$) while items under part 2 gained a Cronbach Alpha result of ($\alpha=.817$) which signified that all items were "Acceptable." On one hand, the researchers used simple random sampling technique to select the participation of 200 public school teachers in the Philippines. There were 100 junior high school teachers and 100 elementary school teachers. The researchers used a Google Form which served as the platform in administering the survey-questionnaire. When the data have been completed, the researchers stored them using MS Excel. Apparently, data analysis technique used in this study involved the use of mean, standard deviation and general weighted mean in order to assess the perceptions of teachers on the significance and influence of methodological choices in developing educational researches. Also, Pearson R was used in order to examine if there would be a significant relationship between teachers' perceptions on the significance of methodological choices and the perceived influence of methodological choices in developing educational researches. The researchers followed strict ethical protocols and rules in conducting an independent research study. They used informed consent, short orientation and formal communication letters as means to ensure that such protocols were followed religiously. Also, gathered data were deleted on the researchers' personal devices after this study was completed and finalized. The respondents were provided a short letter of appreciation in recognition of their active participation during the conduct of this study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Educational researches were central on the continued development of teaching profession, educational management and supervision and other interrelated disciplines concerning education. Researchers in the field of education were keen and mindful on the practical significance of selecting and utilizing different research methods across different types of researches. Fundamentally, three (3) distinct types of research were commonly used in educational researches specially teachers which included quantitative, qualitative and mixed methods. The development and construction of educational researches showed significant considerations, and one of these considerations was the proper and right selection of research methodologies to be used. In this line, research methodology served as the scientific backbone by which educational researches could be directed. In other words, research methodology contained technical and scientific procedures on what, when and how such research work would be administered. With this, teachers' perceptions on the significance and influence of methodological choices on outcomes of educational researches were imperative to assess as it could lay foundation whether they held founded understanding in the selection, utilization and implementation of such research methodology in doing educational researches.

1. **Teachers' Perceptions on the Significance of Methodological Choices in Conducting Educational Researches.** The result showed that teachers highly perceived the significance of choosing right and

proper research design (wm=3.91), relevant sampling techniques (wm=3.84) and data analysis techniques (wm=3.79). The highest weighted mean showed that teachers strongly recognized the importance of selecting right and proper research design which indicated that teachers believed an appropriate research design was critical for ensuring the credence of their research work. In addition, teachers also perceived that when right and proper research design was selected, it could provide a structured framework wherein it could also lead to the coherent and logical response as it addressed the established research objectives and problems on their educational researches. Meanwhile, the second highest mean indicated that teachers also highly perceived the necessity of selecting appropriate sampling methods. They understood that recognizing a scientific representativeness of a sample could significantly affect the generalizability of their results. The results also implied that teachers perceived selecting appropriate research techniques could accurately reflect the diverse contexts and populations within the educational settings, establishing again the credence and validity of their educational researches conducted. Lastly, the lowest mean signified that teachers highly perceived that data analysis techniques strengthened their methodological rigor. In addition, it also implied that teachers' choice of analytical methods could affect the interpretation of data and the conclusions drawn from their educational research. Hence, proper and relevant data analysis were highly perceived by the teachers as essential methodology for deriving impactful insights and ensuring that findings were accurately discussed. Results of the study supported the study of Penalva (2019) which concluded that descriptive methodology provided that continuity and credence of educational researches. Also, similar study revealed that conclusions and implications to be drawn from the research were highly affected by the choice of methodology being used in researches. Practically, the study implicated that teachers' perceptions pertaining methodological choices in administering educational researches could help develop the quality of researches made in the field of educations, instruction and education-related disciplines.

2. **Teachers' Perceptions on the Influence of Methodological Choices in Developing Educational Researches.** The result showed that teachers highly perceived that methodological Choices influenced outcomes of educational researches in terms of applicability of practice (wm=3.92), reliability of results (wm=3.82) and validity of findings (wm=3.83). The highest mean signified that teachers highly perceived that methodological choices influenced the applicability of practice. This further revealed teachers viewed the importance of selecting appropriate research methodology that could be effectively translated into practical applications within the context of prevailing educational conditions. Also, teachers highly perceived that the necessity of research does not only fall on its theoretical impact but also on the relevance and usability in real-world teaching and learning situations. The second highest mean showed that teachers highly perceived that reliability results forming their methodological choices significantly influenced the consistence and dependability of the research findings. In addition, the result signified that teachers highly perceived the critical role of sound research methodologies in terms of reliability results so that their researches could be replicated and verified by other teacher-researchers or scholars in the field of education. Lastly, teachers also highly perceived that selecting proper and right research methodologies in terms of validity of findings significantly influenced educational researches' accuracy. This also meant that teachers highly perceived the importance of providing credible and meaningful discussions drawn from accurate measures found in methodology section. Apparently, it also revealed that teachers highly perceived that validity was essential to establish a meticulously presented educational researches. Results of the study supported the study of Matos et al. (2023) which concluded that specific dimensions in selecting proper research methodologies included the methodological knowledge, research competencies and pedagogical practices of teachers. Similar study also showed that teachers were sensitive in selecting proper research methodologies as it could produce highly credible research leading to the institution of scientific culture within the field of education, instruction and management.
3. **Relationship Between Teachers' Perceptions on the Significance of Methodological Choices and the Perceived Influence of Methodological Choices in Developing Educational Researches.** There was a moderate positive correlation between the perceived significance of methodological choices in terms of research design and the perceived influence of methodological choices in developing

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educational researches in terms of applicability of practice ($r=.385$). The result implied that as teachers perceived the significance of methodological choices in research design to be higher, they also tend to perceive a greater influence of these choices on the applicability of research findings in educational practice. The findings further indicated that teachers who recognized the importance of selecting appropriate research designs were more likely to believe that these designs impact the applicability of findings in real-world situations. The results practically underscored the critical role that research design played in ensuring that educational researchers yield practical and actionable assertions which teachers could implement as they deliver instruction and perform their teaching responsibilities. Results of the study supported the study of Georgiou et al. (2023) which concluded that teachers showed positive attitude on the influence in selecting proper research methodologies and how these researches translated results into actual practices. Practically, the study implicated that there should be a practical collaboration between teachers and expert education researchers in order to deepen teachers' understanding in selecting research methodologies properly and decisively. With this, it could lead to a more applicable outcomes that directly address prevailing educational needs, concerns and gaps.

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CONCLUSION

Teachers highly perceived methodological choices as highly technical because it laid the foundation of a well-established scholarly work emphasizing applicability of practice, reliability of results and validity of findings. On the other hand, there was a moderate positive correlation between the perceived significance of methodological choices in terms of research design and the perceived influence of methodological choices in developing educational researches in terms of applicability of practice which indicated that as teachers perceived the significance of methodological choices in research design to be higher, they also tend to perceive a greater influence of these choices on the applicability of research findings in educational practice.

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